

SIGNIFICANT FEATURES OF ORGANIZING SUCCESSFUL SITUATIONS FOR STUDENTS

Ganieva Gulistan

Karakalpak State University, independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10886489>

Abstract. *In the given article the pedagogy of success, its specific directions, directions for achieving success, the possibility of creating situations of success for students, a description of success, the content of research in this direction, important aspects of situations of success for personal development are discussed. The article serves as a resource for the scientific and pedagogical community, students, teachers and researchers.*

Keywords: *success, pedagogy of success, students, situations, teachers, activity, development, self-improvement, biological success, personal success, motivation, status, group, need.*

It is important to suggest, that the main factor in students' success is their academic performance. Naturally achieved success manifests itself only when a person achieves the goal that has been set for oneself. In this case, the natural needs of the student and used pedagogical tools are important. In the Encyclopedia of Pedagogy, situations of success are defined as follows: situations that develop the mental actions of students, encouraging them to succeed are partially challenging 1.

Definitely, situations of success create a favorable opportunity for future teachers to develop a positive attitude towards the educational process and for students to become more active. As a result, future teachers develop professional creative skills and competencies. Certain qualities are formed in students situations of success. These are: having a positive attitude towards the learning process, being inspired by achievements, and easily overcoming difficulties; It manifests itself in intellectual activity, the desire to cooperating with classmates and teachers, a feeling of satisfaction with one's achievements, creativity and the desire for independent learning and development.

For creating situations of success for students, professors and teachers need to create a innovative environment in the group, encourage them to cooperate and create a favorable environment for mutual support. Natural success situations are a regular process that helps students realize their latent potential. As a result, they regularly seek to showcase their activities.

Certainly, a natural question can be arisen about what pedagogical conditions are necessary for organizing successful situations. To find the answer to this question, it is necessary to identify a system of factors that lead students to successful situations. These factors include objective laws of life, natural, social and personal needs. Understanding the essence of these needs, assimilation of knowledge about them and their use make it possible to ensure the independence of students. Success is a relatively new area of pedagogy, which today attracts most specialists. Situations of success generally attract the attention of not only teachers, but also philosophers, sociologists and psychologists. That is why the category of success and problems of life success are philosophers: Socrates, Plato, Abu Nasr Farabi, modern philosophers N. Shermammedova, F. Nietzsche, C. Pierce, W. James, S. Hook, E. Fromm, psychologists: E. Goziev, N. Boymuradov, Dauletova G.M., B.G. Ananyev, I.D. Beks, A.A. Bodalev, R. Burns, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, K.

Rogers, D. McKelland, A. Maslow, H. Heckhausen, sociologists: M. Weber, E. Durkheim, K. Davis, T. Parsons, P. Sorokin, V. A. Yadov's teachers: A.G. Munavvarov, R. Mavlyanova, R. Safarova, N. Dilova, K. Turgunboev, K. M. Gulyamov, A. S. Belkin, S. U. Goncharenko, M. V. Kondratyeva, A. S. Makarenko, V. A. Sukhomlinsky, G. V. Nikishina, K. D. Developed by such specialists as Ushinsky.

The success of each student depends on the originality and creativity in work. These qualities take on an individual character. Using someone else's experience is the result of a creative approach to this experience.

In the course of independent activity, students rely on many social norms that make special demands on the subject of activity. This is accomplished through different levels of normative knowledge. Student achievement shows general, consistent, and repeatable gains. Because there are laws, models and recommendations that lead to success in all types of human activity. The main law of success is general normative knowledge, the use of which determines the strategy of action. As a result, students will be able to achieve objective results in the process of activity. Normative knowledge, how to achieve the goal? makes it easier to answer the question. Accordingly, the laws of success, models and recommendations are related to the objective laws of life, creating favorable conditions for achieving objective goals, that is, transforming natural knowledge into forms of activity that ensure the achievement of objective laws.

It is not a secret that the main success factor is the student's personal wishes. Personal desire, as the main factor of success, is the first step to success. In this process, a person carries out his activities. A person's desires are based on his needs. A person's desires reflect personal aspirations aimed at satisfying a specific need. It should be emphasized that there are needs associated with desire and needs that appear as a result of necessity.

Desire-related needs are easily satisfied, while necessity-related needs are satisfied with greater effort. In this process, conflicts arise between the actions that need to be performed and the reluctance to perform them. In the process of bringing students to successful situations, it becomes necessary to resolve conflicts between their wants and needs. In most cases, there are also needs that are difficult to satisfy. Objective needs form the basis for the success achieved as a result of one's activities. For doing this, students must ask themselves, "What do I want?" they must be able to answer the question clearly. A balance must be struck between the positive wants and needs of students.

Besides that, desires have the power to influence a person. Strong desires are passions that regularly evoke these emotions. At the same time, it has the ability to influence surrounding people and leads to the concentration of a person's knowledge and attention at one point. Man is very different from other creatures because of his unlimited needs. Satisfied needs are the basis for the emergence of higher-level needs. Models for satisfying needs also change regularly. Students should try to satisfy their natural needs during classes. Because such needs are considered natural, thoughtful and justified.

Satisfying deeply thought-out, reasonable needs serve to ensure personal development. Such needs include the desire to search for naturalness, the need for beauty, the desire to do good, and creative development. Deeply thought-out needs correspond to moral standards, rather than deny them. Satisfying human needs is a limitation in relation to natural resources. A person's need for creative development is the basis for self-improvement and opens up unlimited possibilities for him.

The second important factor for success is clarity of goals. Achieving desired results requires a person to set a clear goal. To achieve success, a person must set specific goals based on his natural desires. The condition that ensures the clarity of the goal is its naturalness. Clarity of goals guarantees a person's success to a certain extent. Because goals clearly define the direction of activity and allow you to select the means and conditions for achieving results accordingly. Clarity of goals ensures that a person is clear about the results of the activity. Such goals are the basis of a person's passion, motivation and inspiration.

The main source of motivation for personal development is clarity of goals. At the same time, clarity of goals indicates the presence of real opportunities to achieve them. A clear definition of life goals and aspirations and their implementation ensures a person's health and peace of mind. By providing peace of mind, renowned psychologist William Glasser has helped many people return to a peaceful life. According to the psychologist, mental disorders arise due to the fact that a person incorrectly defines his goals. Bundy argues that people can't choose their careers and don't finish what they start.

The third key to success is prioritization. A person carrying out his activities sets himself many different regional goals. That is why goals are divided into priority and non-priority. Depending on their nature, these are important, moderately important and less important areas.

Using the Pareto principle is putting students in situations of success will definitely increase the chances of success. Because within the framework of this principle, group members achieve great results. It is promising to carry out one's activities in this process, and its special types guide students towards development.

The pedagogy of success has its own essence, that provides an opportunity to prepare future teachers with a high level of professional competence and pedagogical excellence. For doing this, learners need to study the mechanisms of success. In addition, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for students to succeed. Researching into these questions occurs within the relatively new field of achievement pedagogy.

Undeniably, success pedagogy is an important branch of pedagogy that deals with the activation of the internal capabilities of learners. Learners are able to carry out their educational achievements throughout their life activities. The main goal of creating success situations is to identify the individual's capabilities, activate their abilities, guide them to self-development, encourage them to improve their activities, and provide methods of effective activity in life situations.

In conclusion it should be suggested that that all types of success, the concept of biological success takes priority. A person's desire to achieve success is directly related to his innate physical qualities. It is manifested in the acquisition of high-level thinking skills, as well as physical strength, rapid behavioral stereotypes. Such individuals will have the opportunity to take a clear direction in non-standard situations, show the qualities of courage and activity. This allows learners to occupy a high position among their group and society. Therefore, improving the methodological support for creating success situations for future teachers in the process of training is gaining special relevance today.

REFERENCES

1. Pedagogy: Volume II of the encyclopedia/editor: team – T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2015. – pp.353-373.

2. Safarova R. and b. Contents of the process of developing students' cooperation skills based on friendly relations: a methodological guide. – T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2015. – 216 p.
3. Dauletova G. M. Socio-psychological characteristics and criteria for the adaptation of adolescents to the life of a military academic lyceum (using the example of the military academic lyceum “Temurbek School”), Scientific, theoretical and methodological journal “Pedagogical Mastery”. 2023, no. 9, pp. 106-112.
4. Gulyamov K.M. Structural content of professional competence of a future teacher of applied arts. Professional education No. 1, 2020. pp. 19-22.
5. Mavlyanova R.A. and b. Innovations in primary education (methodological manual). - T. TDPU, 2007. – 181 p.
6. Boymurodov N. Practical psychology. – T.: Generation of the new century, 2008. – 316 p.